

PRESERVING SPREADSHEETS WITH OPEN STANDARDS: A COLLABORATIVE APPROACH

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Abstract – This paper outlines a collaborative initiative by European national archives within the Open Preservation Foundation (OPF) to address the long-term preservation of spreadsheet data. Recognising the risks associated with vendor lock-in and the ephemeral nature of commercial software solutions, the group focused on adopting and extending the OpenDocument Spreadsheet format (ISO 26300), an open standard. They developed a free and open-source (FOSS) validation tool to ensure compliance with both the standard and additional archival requirements, such as disallowing encryption and macros. This case study demonstrates the benefits of community-driven development, open standards, and FOSS tools for digital preservation, highlighting the importance of organisations like the OPF in maintaining long-term access to information.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Many archival institutions utilize commercial services or partnerships to preserve digital content. Planning for what happens if a supplier or partner goes out of business is a standard practice for such arrangements. Today's average corporate lifetime is

historically short, and the evidence suggests it's decreasing.

If commercial partnerships are likely to prove short-lived in archival terms, is there a more effective way to protect against technological obsolescence?

At the Open Preservation Foundation, we believe in the importance of community-maintained open standards and collaborative development of free open-source software solutions for digital preservation. One such solution is validation software, which helps assure organisations that the content they are receiving complies with format specifications. In this short paper we present such an approach, adopted by a small community of European national archives for the preservation of spreadsheet data.

II. PROPRIETARY FORMATS AND COMMERCIAL PARTNERSHIPS

Most archival institutions are working under increasingly strict financial constraints. When governments cut budgets, the burden often falls more heavily on cultural and memory institutions. Commercial solutions and partnerships can be valuable to organisations on tight budgets. When embarking on such ventures, analysing a partner's

likely longevity is standard due diligence. It is sobering to note that the average lifetime of a company listed on the S&P 500 is now estimated to be around 15-30 years, down from around 60 years in the 1950s [1]. This is a global trend with few exceptions; indeed, the average lifespan of a UK company is now less than 9 years, and 50% of small/medium enterprises aren't around to celebrate their fifth birthday. Factors contributing to this include mergers and takeovers, increasing competition, and rapid technological change. The trend is accelerating, and probabilities dictate that most companies will prove ephemeral over archival periods.

Suggesting that memory institutions avoid proprietary file formats altogether is impractical. That said, we believe that adopting formats and tools that aren't tied to a commercial vendor is preferable. Even when a format specification is available as a published standard, other factors may make long-term preservation difficult. Vendors are always searching for new ways to monetise established software. Cloud-based storage and software solutions with subscription models are trends that may have implications for preservation.

III. COMMUNITY INITIATIVE

A. *Inception: The OPF Archive Interest Group*

The OPF Archives Interest Group (AIG) was formed in 2016 by three of the OPF's archive members to collaborate on shared everyday challenges. They began by investigating the significant properties of spreadsheets and what this could mean for archiving and preservation.

Organisations receive increasing numbers of spreadsheets and want to know more about their properties to determine suitable file formats for preservation. The group presented their initial work as a poster at iPres 2019. This won the best poster of the conference. The group continued to build on that work, producing a report on the significant properties of spreadsheets [2] in 2021. This paper presented a deeper analysis of spreadsheet formats using an adapted version of the Investigating the Significant Properties of Electronic Content Over Time (InSPECT) methodology by three national archives, The Danish National Archive (DNA), the National Archive of the Netherlands (NANeth) and

the National Archives of Estonia (NAE). These organisations conducted their analysis via stakeholder interviews. The group found context important when stakeholders considered which properties they deemed significant. Put another way, stakeholders who used a particular feature, such as pivot tables, were likely to feel that the properties supporting pivot tables were significant.

B. *Selection of an Open Specification for Spreadsheet Preservation*

The Danish National Archives' (DNA) interest in the AIG spreadsheet preservation activities arose from practical considerations. DNA mandates the preservation formats they accept by issuing legally binding executive orders. Spreadsheets were preserved via migration to multi-page TIFF/JPEG2000 images. While these are considered secure formats for long-term preservation, it makes reusing the data difficult without effectively remigrating it via techniques like optical character recognition (OCR). Tests were performed by the DNA, where OCR was applied to imaged spreadsheets. The results showed a large amount of data were erroneously recreated through OCR; hence the approach was deemed unfeasible. DNA wanted a suitable format for long-term spreadsheet preservation that enabled data reuse.

DNA worked with the AIG, the OPF, and their stakeholders to choose a suitable preservation format for tabular data. After consideration, the preferred choice was the OpenDocument Spreadsheets format. This is an XML and zip-based format for office documents and applications. It is part of the Open Document Format for Office Applications (ODF), also known as OpenDocument, standardised as ISO 26300 [3].

One reason for choosing the OpenDocument Format is that it is an open standard, developed and maintained by a technical committee in the Organisation for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards [4] (OASIS) consortium. OASIS is a not-for-profit consortium that develops and maintains more than forty standards and associated technical committees. Anyone can contribute to the standard development, and the specification isn't dependent on a specific vendor or software product.

The survival of memories should not depend on pocket depth.

The OpenDocument format guarantees long-term access to data without legal or technical barriers. Organisations and individuals that store their data in an open format, such as OpenDocument, avoid being locked into a single software vendor, leaving them free to switch software if their current vendor goes out of business, raises its prices, changes its software, or changes its licensing terms to something less favourable. Choosing an open standard may be considered as behaving as a good citizen of the archive community.

C. Archival Policy for Spreadsheets

In addition to the ODF format specification, DNA also wished for additional checks for features considered undesirable for long-term preservation. Having chosen a suitable format, work began defining these additional criteria. The completion of this work was marked by the publication of a specification for spreadsheet preservation. This specification was later reduced and revised significantly, but many of the core elements for validation of OpenDocument Format spreadsheets remained.

IV. COLLABORATIVE DEVELOPMENT

In the first half of 2023, DNA proposed the formation of a collaborative group with OPF, the National Archives of the Netherlands and the National Archives of Estonia. Much of the previous work on the preservation specifications and the idea and work needed for setting up an international collaboration was led by Asbjørn Skødt, then a Digital Preservation Officer at the DNA. The work culminated in June 2023 when a formal contractual cooperation agreement was signed. The group aimed to:

- Further develop open and free specifications for digital preservation of spreadsheet file formats. This would extend the official specification by adding further criteria considered undesirable for long-term preservation.
- Develop a Free Open-Source Software (FOSS) tool for validating spreadsheet formats against the OpenDocument and archival specifications.

The participating organisations agreed to fund the development work through periodic payments.

D. Open-source Validation

Existing parsing and validation software was either incomplete or not currently maintained. No software tool existed that would apply additional archival checks to ODF documents. These files are valid according to the specification but may not be recommended for preservation in archival information packages. These include encryption, macros, and references to external data.

The DNA works closely with organisations that submit data to ensure the submission process is as straightforward as possible. Given that they only accept a limited number of formats, file format validation of all submissions is a realistic prospect. Validation is part of the ingest process for new material. Submissions that fail validation are not ingested until the problems are resolved in consultation with the submitting organisation. Ideally, submitters will validate their packaged data before sending it to DNA.

The DNA wanted a validation tool to provide a quality assurance test during submission. While validation is not a complete proxy for rendering, it remains a valuable step in the digital preservation process. Validation checks that objects have been produced correctly and detects errors early during ingest. Valid objects should be easier to render and migrate from in the future. Validation is not a panacea for object preservation. The results of validation failure can be challenging to interpret without detailed knowledge of the file format. Rendering software is forgiving, meaning that files that fail validation may still be rendered perfectly well by software applications.

Open-source was preferred for many reasons. The FOSS ecosystem contributes to the long-term preservation of the software itself. The source code is openly available for use or adaptation; anyone can review it or contribute to the development. The software is free to use and distribute with no proprietary rights or license costs. This allows organisations that submit data to use the same validation software used by the receiving organisation to check the submission. Organisations adopting FOSS tools need a participation model where they involve themselves in open communities rather than behaving as conventional consumers.

E. *Developing the Validator*

The requirements were gathered by consulting the ODF Specifications. These comprise four parts.

- Part one briefly introduces the specification that doesn't address the file format. [5]
- Part two defines the package format for OpenDocument documents. [6]
- Part three briefly covers OpenDocument document conformance and describes the XML schema. [7]
- Part four defines the syntax of the OpenFormula language. [8]

Parts two and three are substantial documents, but much of the content is enforceable programmatically through XML schema validation. The OpenDocument specifications are accompanied by both XML schema (XSD) and RELAX NG documents that specify the structure of the XML files used by the format. These allow automatic validation of these files to ensure they comply with the specification. The remaining requirements concern the structure of OpenDocument packages. These zip archives must be created according to specific rules covering both the file layout and zip features permitted. Part four, the validation of OpenFormula, was considered out of the scope of the funded development.

Development began with coverage of the ODF specifications while the consortium continued to refine the archival criteria. The software was developed in Java for portability and compatibility with existing OPF software. The issues reported by the software fall into four categories:

Package errors: Seven tests that check that the zip archive complies with the specification. This restricts features like the compression algorithms that may be used, and that files required by the specification are present.

Manifest errors: All ODF packages must contain a `manifest.xml` file that lists the files in the package. There are nine manifest tests in total, including checks that files listed in the manifest are present in the package.

Media Type errors: ODF packages may contain a `mimetype` file denoting the document type. There are several restrictions on the properties of this file that ensure it can be used for magic number file

format identification. There are six tests for the properties of this file.

XML validation errors: ODF spreadsheets are predominantly made up of XML files that must comply with a schema. RNG schema [9] are used to validate the files and report any errors found.

A minimal viable product was made available for testing in Q3 2024. Once the spreadsheet preservation specification [10] was finalised, work began on implementing these tests. While some of these rules were implemented as closed tests, many were characterised by the need to detect features in the ODF XML files. These were implemented as a more general test based upon Schematron, an XML language for making assertions about patterns in XML files. The implementation allows users to write schematron tests representing their institution's policy.

Other policy checks allow users to disallow specific versions of the ODF format, check for encryption, macros and external data references.

An alpha of the functionally complete software was delivered in Q2 2024, comprising two Java modules. The library includes an API allowing developers to validate OpenDocument documents and parse their characteristics. The application module uses that API to provide a command-line application that validates OpenDocument files and produces a validation report. It supports all OpenDocument formats and covers the ODF specification's versions 1.0 through 1.3.

F. *Beta Testing and Conversion/Validation Errors*

The software [11] is now in beta testing, with development effort now focused on refinement of the API and documentation. Some issues remain, one of which is the validation of OpenDocument files converted from the Open Office XML (OOXML) format (Microsoft Excel). The conversions tested were performed using the LibreOffice conversion tool. These files fail validation with systemic errors. The problems generally occur when an attribute value isn't converted from OOXML to the OpenDocument equivalent.

Some issues are relatively minor, one example being the conversion of an attribute that denotes the use of a named cell range, `table:range-usable-as`.

Converted files retain the OOXML value “hidden”. This isn’t a legal OpenDocument value; “none” is the closest equivalent. Table ranges are saved cell ranges, i.e. defined groups of spreadsheet cells. They can be used as input to some formulae, as well as to define things like print areas. The issue is unlikely to affect the underlying spreadsheet data.

Another example is the attribute “style:vertical-align” that retains the OOXML value “justify” where OpenDocument only recognises the values “automatic”, “bottom”, “middle” or “top”. Again, this does not affect the table data but may change the way it is presented.

The Danish and Swiss national archives are working with OPF to try to address the conversion issues. While it may be possible to write software to correct the problems, it would be better if the conversion tool produced valid documents. This group is now talking to the OpenDocument Foundation and LibreOffice project with a view to fixing the issues with the converter, by reporting the issues and possibly contributing code patches.

V. WHAT NEXT?

The OPF maintains JHOVE [12], a file validation and characterisation tool developed in Java. Integrating the Java ODF validation library into JHOVE is a logical and straightforward next step. JHOVE also provides a standard graphical user interface for its modules.

OpenDocument Format v1.4 is currently under development, with working drafts published on the OAISIS site. Once this has been finalised, the validator will be extended to cover the new specification.

The validator application options are spreadsheet-centric, unsurprisingly given the project's history. The validation steps for spreadsheets can be applied to any OpenDocument format, e.g. documents, presentations, etc. Options to support validation of any OpenDocument format will be developed for the publicly released software.

OpenFormula validation was left out of the scope of the validator development, despite its utility when validating spreadsheets. The specification describes a language, requiring the development of a parser, which is not a trivial project. It may be possible to

integrate an existing parsing library to implement this feature in future.

The policy checks are useful for determining that a file may contain features that aren't compatible with long-term archiving requirements. Again, these checks reflect DNA's concerns for spreadsheet validation and many of them are not applicable to other OpenDocument formats.

There is no commercially available software to fix files that fail validation or policy checks. Prototype projects have used open-source document SDKs such as Open XML SDK and ODF Toolkit to convert spreadsheet data to comply with the preservation specification. Work still needs to be done to produce viable software.

Finally, open-source software is sustained by the community that uses and supports it. The Open Preservation Foundation will be working with the other members of the consortium to advocate for the use of the specifications and software described in this paper.

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this case study demonstrates the benefits of adopting open standards and developing free and open-source tools for digital preservation. By collaborating, a group of European national archives effectively addressed long-term spreadsheet preservation challenges, mitigating vendor lock-in and technological obsolescence risks. Developing a custom validation tool ensures compliance with the standard and specific archival requirements, providing an essential quality assurance gate for ingest processes. This initiative highlights the power of community-driven development, the sustainability of FOSS ecosystems, and the critical role of organisations like the OPF in maintaining long-term access to information.

Furthermore, it underscores the surprising gap in existing validation tools for office formats, which hold a vast amount of the world's information. The success of this project serves as a model for other institutions facing similar preservation challenges and reinforces the importance of open solutions in the digital age.

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